

International Symposium on Smart Cities: Experiences and Innovations – 2023

Smart Cities for ASEAN ISSCEI 2023

Proceeding Booklet

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ISSCEI 2023

SMART CITIES FOR ASEAN

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AN INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON
SMART CITY FOR ASEAN
Experience and Innovation

ISSCEI
2023

Welcome

By ISSCEI Organizers

We welcome everyone to this conference about ASEAN Smart Cities. The conference gathers representatives from cities, community organizations, industry, and academia. Those with expertise and insights on practical challenges or a keen interest in creative solutions are welcome.

The goal of this conference is to convene thought leaders, practitioners, and researchers to discuss smart city challenges in the ASEAN context and identify applicable technology advances that could underpin sustainable solutions.

TENTATIVE AGENDA OF THE ISSCEI 2023

January 12, 2024

Time	Content
<i>Morning</i>	
7.30 - 8.00	Reception
8.00 - 8.45	Opening ceremony <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome musical performance par MC - Welcome speech from the University of Danang leader - Welcome speech from the City leader Group photo
8.45 - 9.30	Panel Discussion 1: Green technologies for smart cities <i>(Grand conference room)</i> <i>Moderators:</i> Prof. Fabien Ferrero - Professor, The University of d'Azur Prof. Bui Van Ga - Professor, The University of Danang <i>Panelists:</i> Mr. Le Son Phong - Vice-director, Danang Department of Information and Communication Dr. Christian Hartman - Representative of the IRD Institute, French Ministry of Foreign Affairs, in Laos

(Room 804)

13.00 - 13.10: Big Data Analytics for Enhancing Waste Management Systems in Smart Cities - *Nguyen Van Hung, Nguyen Thanh Tuan*

13.10 – 13.20: IoT with Geostationary Satellite using S-Band - *Fabien Ferrero, Manh Thao Nguyen*

13.20 – 13.30: Install sensors and GPS on the car for collecting real-time temperature (and pollution) mapping in ASEAN cities - *Khampasith Chanthavong, Nampheung Sayalath*

13.30 – 13.40: Smart Quality Robot To Assess Student Satisfaction and Assist Student Learning in STEM Education - *Nguyen Ngoc Hoan, Tran Van Dinh Sang, Tran Dinh Tin, Nguyen Thi Anh Thu, Pham Van Tuan*

13.40 - 13.50: Robotic Solution - *Do The Can, Dang Ngoc Tu, Le Tuan Tu*

13.50 - 14.00: Determination of Pol Content in Molasses Using Near-Infrared Spectroscopy and Partial Least Squares Regression - *Le Tuan Phuc, Tran Thi Thanh Hoa, Pham Ngoc Hung, Bui Uyen Diem, Cung Thi To Quynh, Le Thanh Nhan, Hoang Quoc Tuan (online)*

*Chair: Prof. Fabien Ferrero
(Room 806)*

13.00 - 13.10: IoT system for safety monitoring and early warning of tourists using LoRaWAN network - *Van Lic Tran, Le Quoc Huy*

13.10 – 13.20: Effective Integration Of Neural Network and Skin Spectroscopy In Diagnosing Skin Conditions - *Ha Thi Nguyet Tran, Ha Thi Nguyet Tran, Tuan Van Pham, Thu Thi Anh Nguyen*

13.20 – 13.30: Smart Library - *Do The Can, Dang Ngoc Tu, Le Tuan Tu*

13.30 – 13.40: Application of Low-Power Embedded Devices in Water Meter Digit Recognition - *Thai Vu Hien, Van Lic Tran*

13.40 - 13.50: Autonomous Garbage Collecting Robot using Path Planning Algorithm and LoRa Network - *Vinh Tran Dinh, Dat Le Thanh, Tuan Pham Cong Anh, Cuong Chau Van Kim, Huy Le Quoc*

14.00 -15h30

Panel Discussion 2: Smart education for smart cities

Moderators:

Dr. Nguyen Thi Anh Thu - Vice-director, The University of Danang - DNIIT Institute

Panelists:

Assoc.Prof. Vo Van Minh - Rector, and Dr. Le Thi Thanh Tinh - Lecturer, The University of Danang - University of Education and Science

	<p>Mr. Vo Duc Anh - Vice-director, The Startup and Innovation Center of the Danang City</p> <p>Mr. Trinh Quoc Bao - Vice-director, IT Center, VNPT, Danang</p> <p>Dr. Do The Can - Vice-director, Dept. of Personnel and Administration, UD-DUT</p>
9.30 - 10.00	<p>Tea-break & Poster showcase (<i>Grand conference room</i>)</p>
10.00 - 11.20	<p>Technical Session: Technical papers presentation (<i>Room: 804, B building</i>)</p> <p><i>Chair: Dr. Le Quoc Huy</i></p> <p>10.00 - 10.10: Advanced Liquid Assessment via Vector Network Analyzer Integration with Machine Learning Models - <i>Doan Thi Ngoc Canh, Van Lic Tran, Fabien Ferrero, Nhan Le Thanh</i></p> <p>10.10 – 10.20: Smart Farm - <i>Do The Can, Dang Ngoc Tu, Le Tuan Tu</i></p> <p>10.10 – 10.20: Utilizing LoRaWAN Network for Water Quality Monitoring - <i>Van Lic Tran, Thanh Long Vu</i></p> <p>10.30 – 10.40: Using i-Tree canopy for assessing urban tree cover in Danang City – <i>Ngoc Son Tran, Minh Hieu Ha, Thi Kim Phuong Nguyen, Van Chuong Hoang</i></p> <p>10.50 – 11.00: Building a real-time geospatial visualization for flood forecasting - <i>Chris Santamaria, N. Rich Nguyen (online)</i>.</p> <p>11.00 – 11.10: Smart approach to green campus: challenges and recommendations for the Vietnamese higher education institutions - <i>Thi Kinh Kieu, Van Khanh Nguyen (online)</i>.</p> <p>11.10 – 11.20: Beer Type Classification Based on Electromagnetic Waves Using Vector Network Analyzer with Machine Learning Model - <i>Le Tuan Phuc, Tran Thi Thanh Hoa, Pham Ngoc Hung, Nguyen Ngoc Vien, Cung Thi To Quynh, Le Thanh Nhan, Hoang Quoc Tuan (online)</i>.</p> <p>11.20 – 11.30: Preserving Danang's historical values for smart tourism city - <i>Phan Bao An, Le Thi Kim Anh</i>.</p>
<i>Luncheon</i>	
<i>Afternoon</i>	
13.00 - 14.00	<p>Technical Session 2: Technical papers presentation (<i>Room: 804 and 806, B building</i>)</p> <p><i>Chair: Assoc.Prof. Pham Van Tuan</i></p>

	Assoc.Prof. Pham Van Tuan - Rector, LYDINC Institute Prof. Fabien Ferrero - Prof. Fabien Ferrero - Professor, The University of d'Azur
15.30	Tea-break & Poster showcase (<i>Grand conference room</i>)
16.00	Closing

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OPENING SPEECH

GREETINGS FROM THE UNIVERSITY OF DANANG

Assoc.Prof.Dr. Le Quang Son
Vice President of the University of Danang

DISCUSSION PANEL 1

GREEN TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE SMART CITY

**MODERATED BY
PROF. BUI VAN GA; PROF. FABIEN**

DISCUSSION PANEL 2

SMART EDUCATION FOR THE SMART CITY

**MODERATED BY
Dr NGUYEN THI ANH THU**

Advanced Liquid Assessment via Vector Network Analyzer Integration with Machine Learning Models

by Thi Ngoc Canh DOAN (canhdtm@due.edu.vn), Van Lic TRAN (tvlic@dut.udn.vn), Fabien FERRERO (fabien.ferrero@univ-cotedazur.fr), Nhan Le-Thanh (nhan.le-thanh@univ-cotedazur.fr)

1. Project objectives

Developing efficient, precise, portable, and cost-effective instruments for liquid assessment stands as a crucial area, especially when discerning the quality characteristics of a diverse range of liquid consumables. This encompasses alcoholic beverages like red wines, rice wines, and beers, as well as non-alcoholic drinks such as juices, fruit-based vinegars, coffee mixes, and cola variants. Additionally, it covers dairy items like milk and yogurt, and various oils like vegetable, camellia, peanut, extra virgin olive, and frying oils. Within this study, we introduce a novel technique leveraging the NanoVNA. This method emits a targeted signal via a specific antenna, then captures both the reflected and transmitted signals upon interaction with the sample. These interactions are defined by metrics S_{11} and S_{21} . By testing with various liquids, the system's efficacy in distinguishing between different types is demonstrated. Experiments conducted with samples like filtered water, Huda beer, Hanoi beer, Vietnamese beer, and Nam Vodka show distinct signatures for each type. Furthermore, the research also delves into identifying and verifying potential adulterations.

2. Brief of smart city technology

The gathered data comprises S-parameters, elucidating the relationship between inputs and outputs among ports in an electrical setup. Within NanoVNA, there are two ports, denoted as Port 0 and Port 1. In Port 0, S_{11} holds significance when discussing antennas—it signifies the extent of power reflected from the antenna, commonly termed as the reflection coefficient (also referred to as gamma or return loss). The remaining power is either absorbed or radiated by the antenna. Typically, antennas are engineered for minimal loss, aiming to maximize radiated power. Port 1, on the other hand, portrays S_{21} , indicating the power transfer from Port 0 to Port 1, known as the transmission coefficient. The apparatus used for measurement, alongside the antenna.

To obtain S_{11} and S_{21} , the nanoVNASaver software, developed by Rune B. Broberg, comes into play. This versatile tool is employed across multiple platforms to save Touchstone files from NanoVNA. It establishes a connection with the NanoVNA, retrieves the data, and stores Touchstone files on the computer.

Figure 1: An example of two-port network.

In this study, we collected VNA data from five liquids: water, wine, Hanoi beer, Huda beer, and Viet beer. Each type of liquid will have distinct characteristics and properties, such as color, concentration, etc. This leads to varying reflection waves and penetration depths for each type of liquid, resulting in distinct waveforms for each liquid type in the collected data. Totally, we have collected 1000 VNA measurements, each of which has the frequency of 700MHz – 1.5GHz and an antenna with a frequency of 923MHz.

Figure 2: Images of data for all liquids (30 samples/type) on Matlab.

3. Anticipated Impact

The project, if practically applied, can combat counterfeiting in food, ensure human health with simple, inexpensive and easy-to-use equipment.

4. Potential Challenges

This paper presents the first attempt in applying VNA measurements for liquid recognition in Vietnam. We have used machine learning solutions for automatic recognition of five types of liquids, which are filtered water, Huda beer, Hanoi beer, Vietnamese beer, and Nam Vodka. First results confirm the potential of applying NanoVNA and machine learning technologies for liquid analysis. However, we have some challenges such as the need a large number of samples.

5. Collaboration opportunities

There will be a collaboration among food research units or supermarkets to provide standard samples which lead to more accurate data analysis and data classification. As a result, the commercialization of this product can be supported by the company.

SMART FARM

by [Do The Can, dtcan@dut.udn.vn , University of Science and Tecnology, Dang Ngoc Tu, dangngoctu04@gmail.com, Le Tuan Tu, tult0409@gmail.com]

1. Smart Farm objectives

Abstract: Smart Farm explores the synergy of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Automation in agriculture. AI provides valuable real-time insights for informed decision-making, while Automation streamlines traditional tasks through robotics, enhancing operational efficiency. The integration mainly aims to significantly boost productivity, resource efficiency, and sustainability in modern farming.

<https://smartfarmapp.azurewebsites.net>

Keywords: Smart Farm, Modern Agriculture, Smart City.

Introduction: Enhancing the quality of life through advanced technology is a top priority for Da Nang city management and technology organizations. The Smart Farm initiative, focusing on smart agriculture, resource management, and urban solutions, aims to optimize the living environment and promote sustainable development and a green economy in Da Nang.

2. Brief of smart city technology

Methodology: In this project, we employed a mixed-methods approach by integrating data analysis from scholarly articles and statistical findings from various sources. The synthesis of quantitative and qualitative data aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. The seamless amalgamation of these analyses yielded synchronized information, facilitating a reasonable selection of technologies within the project framework.

Technology:

IoT: Utilizing integrated sensors and cameras on the Auto Farm, data is visually transmitted to the web platform via Firebase. This enables users to remotely effective monitor the garden's status. Additionally, IoT technology empowers users to effectively control and manage plant care through automated mechanisms within the garden, facilitated by the Administrative Web interface.

Integration of ML/AI and Web: We have implemented Artificial Intelligence (AI) models trained on high-accuracy datasets sourced from *Kaggle.com*. These seamlessly integrated models within the web interface facilitate uniform disease detection and plant status monitoring. Users also possess the capability to query information on plant diseases based on available images or images taken by camera through the web interface.

Automation: Within the Auto Farm framework, we have strategically designed and integrated mechanical structures to facilitate the automation of various agricultural tasks. These tasks span the spectrum from the precise process of seeding to the intricate activities of irrigation and overall crop care. The amalgamation of parameters derived from the Internet of Things (IoT) system not only renders these agricultural operations entirely autonomous but also contributes significantly to enhancing their overall efficiency.

3. Anticipated Impact

Results:

Web: Our website integrates AI models based on accurate data and images extracted from cameras in Smart Farm to make precise determinations about the condition and diseases of plants. Furthermore, our system suggests treatment regimens. In addition, real-time monitoring of the transmitted data on the web facilitates easier garden management and control for users.

Farm: The design of a prototypical Auto Farm model, encompassing an area of 40x60cm, has been successfully accomplished. The autonomous functionalities, notably the precision seeding and irrigation systems, exhibit consistent and efficient performance devoid of constant surveillance. Strategically deployed sensors and cameras facilitate the accurate transmission of data to Web Firebase, ensuring a seamless and continuous synchronization of information from the Smart Farm to the designated database.

4. Potential Challenges

The challenges of Smart Farming encompass a multitude of complex and diverse factors:

- ❑ **Technology Compatibility:** Synchronizing and integrating various technologies, from sensors and cameras to artificial intelligence systems, requires high compatibility among components, especially when developed by different providers.
- ❑ **Costs and Financial Risks:** Initial investments in deploying Smart Farming can be high, especially for small-scale farmers and agricultural businesses. Financial risks from technical glitches and price fluctuations may impact acceptance and widespread implementation.

Utilizing LoRaWAN Network for Water Quality Monitoring

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1. Project objectives

The aim of the project is to design a system for measuring various parameters of the aquaculture environment, including pH levels, dissolved oxygen concentration in water, and water turbidity. These parameters are synthesized by a control unit and sent to a server for display on the application interface for users. Alerts are sent to users when the water parameters exceed certain thresholds, either too low or too high. Users can access a specially designed website to view the water parameters.

2. Brief of technology

The methodology for water monitoring via a LoRaWAN network presents an innovative approach poised to revolutionize the management of aquatic environments. Its foundational principle involves the strategic deployment of specialized sensors equipped with LoRaWAN communication modules. These sensors, meticulously stationed at key locations within water bodies, serve as sentinels, continuously collecting a wealth of data pertaining to critical water parameters. This comprehensive suite of measurements includes pH levels, dissolved oxygen content, turbidity, and temperature. The amalgamation of these diverse parameters captures a nuanced understanding of the aquatic ecosystem's health and stability.

Facilitating the seamless transmission of this data is the LoRaWAN network infrastructure, comprising gateways and a central server. This network acts as a conduit, facilitating the wireless transmission of data packets from the sensors to the central server. Upon reception, the central server undertakes a multifaceted role, serving as the nerve center for data aggregation, processing, and analysis in real time. Employing sophisticated algorithms, the system filters, validates, and processes the incoming data streams, ensuring accuracy, identifying anomalies, and discerning patterns within the dataset.

The significance of this methodology lies not merely in data collection but in its translation into actionable insights. The processed data is elegantly presented through an intuitive user interface, empowering stakeholders with real-time access to critical water parameters. This interface facilitates multifaceted functionalities, including live monitoring, historical trend analysis, and the establishment of customizable alerts for crucial thresholds. The proactive alert mechanism, a cornerstone of the system, promptly notifies users of deviations in water quality parameters, enabling swift interventions to maintain optimal conditions for aquatic life.

Figure 1. System block diagram

Figure 2: Water monitoring prototype

3. Anticipated Impact

Implementing this LoRaWAN-based water monitoring system is anticipated to optimize aquaculture practices by enabling real-time monitoring, proactive interventions, and informed decision-making for sustainable resource management.

4. Potential Challenges

While promising, the implementation of a LoRaWAN-based water monitoring system may face challenges such as network coverage limitations in remote areas, potential data transmission interferences, the need for periodic sensor maintenance for accurate readings, and ensuring secure data transfer and storage to prevent breaches, all of which require robust solutions for the system's effective and reliable operation.

5. Collaboration opportunities

There will be a collaboration with fish farming. As a result, the commercialization of this product can be supported by the company.

USING i-TREE CANOPY FOR ASSESSING URBAN TREE COVER IN DANANG CITY

by Ngoc-Son Tran (tnson@ued.udn.vn),
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GreenViet Biodiversity Conservation Centre

1. Project objectives

Urban trees provide many benefits to the residential community, including minimizing the impact of climate change, reducing energy for buildings, improving air quality, and improving human health (Nowak et al., Pace et al., 2018). Urban canopy cover refers to the area of the ground covered by the crown of healthy trees, including leaves, branches, and stems, when viewed from above.

Management solutions aim to increase overall urban tree cover (UTC), species diversity, and tree size to optimize the provision of ecosystem services (Ordonez and Duinker, 2013). Numerous nations have established ambitious objectives to increase the proportion of tree cover in urban areas, such as through “Million Tree” or “Billion Tree” campaigns in the USA and Vietnam (McPherson et al., 2011; Vietnamnews.vn, 2021). Overall percent tree cover ranging from less than 20% to about 50% canopy cover is ideal (Nowak et al., 1996; UFWACN, 2018).

Tree cover is important fundamental data for city management decisions, planning, and policy development. However, research about estimating urban tree cover is quite limited in Vietnam compared to other countries. The four main methods for determining UTC are crown cover scale, transect, dot, and scan. This research focuses on cover percentages and changes within six urban areas of Danang city based on the dot method in i-Tree Canopy.

2. Brief of smart city technology

i-Tree model has been developed by the Davey Institute and the USDA Forest Service (the US) since 2006 to provide urban and rural forestry analysis and benefits assessment tools. The i-Tree tools, including i-Tree Eco, i-Tree Canopy, i-Tree Design, i-Tree Landscape, and i-Tree Hydro), can help strengthen forest management and advocacy efforts by quantifying forest structure and trees' environmental benefits. Of these, i-Tree Canopy is used to classify land and tree cover across a given area using random sampling of aerial imagery

linked with <https://www.google.com/maps>. Four surface classifications, including Trees, Impervious Shrubs/Grass, and water, were examined in six urban districts in Danang city.

Figure 1. i-Tree canopy model was used to evaluate the urban tree cover in Danang city

Table 1. Change in cover classes in 6 urban districts between 2015-2023

Districts	Area (Km ²)	Cover	2015		2023		Cover changes (%)
			%	SE	%	SE	
Cam Le	12.93	Imperviousness	41.8	0.87	54.5	0.96	12.7
		Shrub	28.27	1.16	10.67	0.80	-17.6
		Tree	22.40	1.08	27.33	1.15	4.9
		Water	7.53	0.68	7.53	0.68	0.0
Hai Chau	8.69	Imperviousness	62.3	1.12	62.8	1.12	0.5
		Shrub	6.67	0.72	6.17	0.69	-0.5
		Tree	19.42	1.14	19.42	1.14	0.0
		Water	11.58	0.92	11.58	0.92	0.0
Lien Chieu	16.79	Imperviousness	51.2	0.86	61.6	0.91	10.4
		Shrub	27.49	1.07	14.35	0.84	-13.1
		Tree	16.86	0.89	18.12	0.92	1.3
		Water	4.46	0.49	5.95	0.57	1.5
Ngu Hanh Son	15.57	Imperviousness	45.8	0.82	51.6	0.86	5.8
		Shrub	29.82	1.08	16.28	0.87	-13.5
		Tree	14.05	0.82	19.89	0.94	5.8
		Water	10.33	0.72	12.22	0.77	1.9
Son Tra	6.36	Imperviousness	67.3	1.41	66.9	1.39	-0.4
		Shrub	8.88	1.01	6.63	0.88	-2.3
		Tree	14.00	1.23	17.13	1.33	3.1
		Water	9.88	1.05	9.38	1.03	-0.5
Thanh Khe	3.67	Imperviousness	72.2	1.66	73.2	1.68	1.0
		Shrub	7.20	1.16	6.60	1.11	-0.6
		Tree	16.00	1.64	15.60	1.62	-0.4
		Water	4.60	0.94	4.60	0.94	0.0

Figure 2. Change in cover classes in Danang city between 2015 and 2023

The results showed that the tree of other cover types has changed from 2015 to 2023. Of these, the percentage of tree cover increased from 17.3% to 20.3% and water cover slightly rose to 8.9% in 2023. The impervious type increased significantly from 52.9% to 59.3% a rise of roughly 409 ha. Noticeably, Shrub/grass cover declined sharply from 21.6% in 2015 to 11.4% in 2023, or a loss of about 648 ha within 8 years.

3. Anticipated Impact

Currently, Vietnam needs more data on the current status of urban tree cover. i-Tree Canopy is an easy-to-use, free, and highly accurate tool that can support the development of policies to increase tree coverage to meet Resolution No. 06-NQ/TW dated December 24, 01/2022 on planning, construction, management, and sustainable urban development in Vietnam to 2030, vision to 2045.

4. Potential Challenges

The i-Tree Canopy tool for estimating urban tree cover and other classes' cover is based on the linking of Google Maps and Google Earth imagery. However, older images in the previous 2015 were low-resolution which made it difficult to assess the class cover changes in urbans in Vietnam in that period.

5. Collaboration opportunities

Coordinating the Department of Construction to estimate the green cover of each area and provide solutions such as proposing the number of trees and tree species needed for planting to achieve the goal of tree cover percent for Da Nang city or other large cities.

Acknowledgments: We are grateful to the U.S. Forest Service and GreenViet Biodiversity Conservation Centre for providing us with technical training and funding through the i-Tree International Program.

Building a real-time geospatial visualization for flood forecasting

by Chris Santamaria (chris@santamaria.me) and N. Rich Nguyen (nn4pi@virginia.edu), University of Virginia

1. Project objectives

The tenacious threat of floods can strain a nation's disaster management resources and pose significant challenges to sustainable development. There is an urgent and critical need to develop and implement advanced, practical tools and strategies for flood prediction and mitigation [1]. FloodWatch is a web platform offering real-time flood forecasting and crowd-sourced reporting. The platform primarily seeks to aid citizens in Vietnam, especially those in regions susceptible to coastal flooding, such as Da Nang and Ho Chi Minh City. Effectively informing users of relative flood risk in their region has become a significant area of focus. This report will describe the design and implementation of FloodWatch's "region tileset" feature, which visualizes approximately 20,000 daily collected weather readings to serve citizens through an intuitive map-based user interface.

2. Brief of smart city technology

Previously, the visualization on Floodwatch was implemented as markers per-city basis, focusing on the most populated cities across Vietnam. In practice, we found individual markers to be a severe limitation. For example, major regions like Ho Chi Minh City often had several nearby markers, but they failed to offer the granularity we sought to provide users. Similarly, lower population regions were often completely unrepresented, providing no value to residing citizens. In this report, we propose a multi-level region-based visualization approach. Rather than displaying individual *weather collection points*, we show shaded boundaries representing regions across Vietnam. The fill color visualizes the average flood risk score across all collection points within the boundary, providing a more holistic representation of a region than a single point. Regions are based on "administrative divisions" (AMD) defined by the Database of Global Administrative Areas [2].

Collecting data for multiple levels enables visualization of flood risk from high-level provinces to low-level neighborhoods. Input data is defined according to the GeoJSON specification [3]: regions are represented as *Feature* objects, and each *Feature* contains properties such as region name and AMD level. Given an input data set, we generate a list of collection points for each *Feature* by four steps: (1) calculate a bounding box around the region; (2) generate random points within the bounding box; (3) perform K-means clustering on the points, and (4) extract its centroid point for each cluster. After completion, the tool saves the resulting GeoJSON, which can be consumed later in the region tileset pipeline. This process is performed for multiple AMD levels --- as boundaries become smaller towards the lower level, the number of generated points per *Feature* similarly decreases. However, higher granularity levels also contain significantly more total points. For example, a low-level AMD generates 6,640 points with the default parameters, while a high-level AMD generates more than double with 13,938 points. The figure below describes the primary process of building region-based AMD levels.

Initial Prototype for per-city markers

Generated collection points from internal tool

Region-based w/ multiple admin levels

With the collection points generated, weather data can be sampled. Our team utilizes a nightly Python script managed via GitHub Actions to provide per-day visualizations, which fetches data for a specified query date. For each GeoJSON data set emitted by the previous tool, centroids within its feature objects are used to query daily average weather data at each point. Once data is collected for all points within a region, readings are averaged to produce a single set of weather properties displayed to the user. Additionally, a flood risk score is computed based on the obtained weather data --- though our team is independently developing an unsupervised learning prediction model, our current generation process uses a relatively simple prediction based on measured precipitation.

3. Anticipated Impact

FloodWatch presents a data distribution platform for citizens, enabling them to make informed choices about their safety through collected weather data and user-submitted flood reports. In addition to representing flood risk through a fill color on the region map overlay, the app also supports tapping individual regions to open a popup containing specific weather information. The notion of live, crowd-sourced flood reports as collection points also presents a new perspective when considering the idea of "technological citizenship," such that citizens can empower and benefit from other citizens through a new form of civic involvement [4].

4. Potential Challenges

Our current approach creates entirely new tilesets for each day processed; given the static nature of our administrative boundary data, we'd prefer only to update the weather data encoded in *Feature* properties while keeping geometry data constant. Currently, we can only change an existing tileset by reprocessing all tiles and effectively recreating the entire tileset. One possible alternative could be decoupling the weather data from the tileset. Rather than generating a complete tileset in our nightly job, we could create a minimal JSON-based file containing only weather data. Once a static tileset has loaded on the client side, we can inject weather data onto the tileset.

5. Collaboration opportunities

More broadly, our team is beginning to shift focus from research-oriented feature experimentation towards polishing the platform for end users. Though the platform can provide immense value to citizens in Vietnam, refining the new user experience and promoting a sense of civic involvement will become crucial aspects of preparing FloodWatch for real-world usage. Early user testing has highlighted a few notable areas of improvement, with the previously mentioned flood risk score being a common area of confusion. To help improve this, we seek independent collaborators to develop a clustering-based unsupervised learning model trained on historical flood data in Vietnam.

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Smart approach to green campus: challenges and recommendations for the Vietnamese higher education institutions

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1. Introduction

Rapid urbanization is turning cities and metropolitan areas into ecological, green, sustainable, and environmental cities. Researchers, decision-makers, and the general public are now more interested than ever in the topics of digital transformation and smart cities, particularly in the wake of the Covid-19 outbreak.

Universities are essential to assisting nations in achieving the 17 SDGs. Universities all throughout the world are changing to keep up with the swift pace of societal change [1–3]. Various approaches, such as green university models, sustainable universities, and smart universities, have been proposed to address the challenge of creating higher education that aligns with societal demands. Waste reduction, smart mobility, green building design, and renewable energy are some of the most promising developments in campus sustainability and green technologies [1, 3–5]. By reducing energy waste with smart sensors, optimizing charging, managing appliances intelligently, and improving energy management, the adoption of IoT technology helps college campuses become more environmentally friendly [1, 6]. Green technology-focused campus programs that are exciting and engaging for students to lead can foster innovation and positive change within their college communities and their community outreach, particularly government and business community [7].

One way to support the development of higher education in a timely and sustainable way is through the collaboration of smart universities and green universities through a diverse, comprehensive, and integrated approach. However, not much research has been done on this topic recently in Vietnam. As a result, this paper examines the benefits and difficulties of incorporating digitalization into Vietnamese institutions' green transformation.

2. Methodology

Traditional literature review was applied to have a overview of the smart and green campus worldwide. Then, snowball sampling was conducted to collect the secondary data and in-depth interviews at the 6 universities in Vietnam, including: Vietnam National University – Hanoi (VNUHN); Vietnam National University-Ho Chi Minh (VNUHCM), University of Economy Ho Chi Minh (UEH); Ton Duc Thang University (TDTU); Hanoi Open University (HOU); The University of Danang – University of Science and Education (UD-UED). Despite the limited sampling number, the research team tried to ensure the diversity in geographical locations (North, Central, South region); in characteristics of university (national, regional, private and autonomous public university); and in training scale. The focus themes of interviews are: (i)

existing implementation of smart and/or green campus; (ii) strategy/vision; and (iii) challenges and opportunities.

3. Key findings

3.1. Commitment and practices towards digital and green transformation

Decree 06/2022/ND-CP on rules to lower greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and to maintain the ozone layer; and Decree 08/2022/ND-CP and Decision No. 01/2022/QD-TTg are only a few of the legislative frameworks that the government has released on reducing GHG emissions, protecting the environment, and responding to climate change. One of the key papers to carry out the digital transformation is the Prime Minister's Decision No. 749/QD-TTg, which approves the "National Digital Transformation Program to 2025, with a vision to 2030", extensive and pervasive digital change across the country. IT application is also emphasized in the field of education through the Prime Minister's Decision No. 131/QD-TTg, approving the Project "Strengthening the application of information technology and digital transformation in education and training period 2022 - 2025, orientation to 2030". Then, the Minister of Education and Training (MOET) issued Decision No. 1282/QD-BGDDT dated May 10, 2022 on promulgating a plan to increase the application of information technology information and digital transformation in education and training for the period 2022-2025 by the MOET.

In light of this, some Vietnamese universities have stated their intention to create smart, green, and sustainable educational institutions. Four of the six universities that were questioned have created strategies and plans for implementation; in particular, Ton Duc Thang University has been certified as a Green University by the UI GreenMetric assessment system [8, 9]. The remaining two universities have performed research on modifying university administration practices and creating university-wide understanding of a sustainable university model. Among the specific practices being implemented in schools are the following:

- Establishing the groundwork for more intelligent and technologically advanced campuses
- Developing internal and external digital awareness and proficiency
- Digitizing the educational process

These approaches have reduced greenhouse gas emissions, increased productivity and efficiency of university administration and operations, decreased consumption (of electricity, water, and paper), and simultaneously decreased instructional expenses. Additionally, research and training initiatives have raised standards and created a wealth of chances for both domestic and international collaboration.

3.2. Challenges and recommendations

There are 3 main obstacles to building green and smart universities in Vietnam:

- i. Lack of financial resources: Many small higher education institutions (HEIs) lack on-site financial resources to carry out digital transformation. The private HEI is favorable in terms of mechanism, but it requires a significant expenditure in terms of premises, facility investment, and luring staff to construct. Although there is pressure on the public HEI to become more self-governing, there are still too many administrative processes that restrict management, investment, and the influence of multiple stakeholders.
- ii. Lack of human resources: The HEI's senior leaders do not comprehend digital transformation, are unaware of the necessity to construct and develop a green university, and the majority are not IT professionals. Technical personnel to carry out the

implementation are insufficiently qualified. If qualified, there is insufficient finance and a competitive working environment to hire and retain personnel when compared to the private HEI.

iii. The physical infrastructure is not synchronized, and the IT infrastructure is inadequate and unequal: The physical facilities are small, dispersed, decentralized, outdated, and incapable of developing or changing the model. There are still very few, if any, newly invested facilities that have been transformed into smart operations. On the other hand, there is little new investment in IT appliances, and they age quickly. If invested, there are insufficient funds for upkeep and advancement. There is not enough data to evaluate with AI software and make advancements because data digitization has not been fully applied.

Based on the current challenge analysis, several solutions are proposed:

i. Create a specialized strategic consulting firm for higher education digital transformation: A survey and assessment of the existing situation on a regional and national scale is required. A set of criteria and prioritized areas for digital transformation should be developed. Each HEI needs to determine an appropriate roadmap based on its resources (human resources, finance, infrastructure, and present status). It is essential to establish an impartial institution to review and rate the level of digital transformation, smart and green universities.

ii. Develop a national model: The National Smart Green University model's success provides proof, lessons learned, and inspiration for the education sectors to improve. Communication is prerequisite to construct commercial and social universities in order to promote awareness and identify development needs.

iii. Invest in the development of a national open-source university management software application warehouse: To decrease costs and startup time, central government should provide free open-source university management software to universities around the country at early stage or provide free smart control solutions on an IoT platform.

iv. Financial incentives, investment incentives, tax incentives, and policies: In order to benefit from favorable tax laws, large tuition margins, and a high degree of autonomy, universities rank their level of digital transformation as smart and green.

4. Conclusion

Smart and green university integrated model is a promising approach to boost the Vietnamese HEIs to keep pace with the development of global higher education. This paper's preliminary study reveals that Vietnam's universities still have a long way to go before implementing digital and green transformation. In addition to the mobilization of internal resources, central government macro intervention is necessary to guarantee the long-term growth of environmentally conscious and smart university

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Beer Type Classification Based on Electromagnetic Waves Using Vector Network Analyzer with Machine Learning Model

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1. Project objectives

Beer of unknown origin may contain flavorings and toxic chemicals, leading to adverse effects on consumers' health. Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) and Frequency Domain Reflectometry (FDR) measurements are non-destructive techniques based on Electromagnetic Waves to determine the typical dielectric constant of certain liquids or solids. The purpose of this study is to investigate the ability to use S parameters, specifically S11 (reflection coefficient) and S21 (transmission coefficient) of a vector network analyzer NanoVNA, to distinguish between different types of beer.

2. Brief of the Regression Method

Beer includes 5 canned beer samples available on the Vietnamese market. Samples were collected and transferred to the laboratory of the Center for Food Product Research and Development (Hanoi University of Science and Technology). Beer samples are stored in the refrigerator, maintained at a temperature of 6-8°C. Pour beer into the cuvette of the device, tilting it 45 degrees so that the clear beer submerges above the antenna. Conduct measurements using nanoVNAsaver software, with each sample measured with 10 consecutive values. Each can of beer is measured six times. Experiments were performed in a Faraday cage (a cardboard box measuring 30x40x30cm and covered with foil to limit the influence of externally induced electric forces or electromagnetic fields).

To develop a method for distinguishing between beer types using electromagnetic waves, the following steps were executed: data files were gathered from the NanoVNA network analyzer in *.s2p file format and subsequently merged. The subsequent section involves calculating the magnitudes of the parameters S11 and S21, with the results combined into

distinct datasets for S11 and S21. Data preprocessing included checking for any missing values and experimenting with data normalization methods to identify the most optimal approach. The dataset was then divided into two parts (Training 70% and Testing 30%), and the classification model was applied and evaluated based on the accuracy score.

Various preprocessing methods, including multiple scatter correction (MSC), standard normal variate (SNV), and first and second derivative Savitzky–Golay (SG), were applied. In the case of parameter S1, the Random Forest Model with SG1 preprocessing demonstrated the most accurate prediction at 95%. Conversely, for the S2 parameter, the Random Forest Model with SG2 preprocessing yielded the best prediction accuracy at 92%. This result demonstrates the potential of a novel method that utilizes electromagnetic waves to distinguish between different beer samples.

3. Anticipated Impact

The impact of this research is to provide a rapid, non-destructive method that can be performed directly in the field to identification beer types. The application of fast, non-destructive prediction methods distinguishes between genuine and counterfeit products and contributes to economic benefits and human health protection.

4. Potential Challenges

Although these results show promise, further research and development are necessary to achieve a more accurate prediction model. This entails constructing a more diverse database encompassing various types of beer and implementing a more robust classification model.

5. Collaboration opportunities

Beer companies can collaborate to diversify beer samples, aiming to construct a model that effectively distinguishes between various beer samples. Another opportunity lies in quality analysis laboratories, which can aid in assessing the quality of beer ingredients, enabling the construction of regression models for predicting beer quality.

6. Acknowledgments

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PRESERVING DANANG'S HISTORICAL VALUES FOR SMART TOURISM CITY

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1. Project objectives

From analyzing the distribution and transportation of tourists from various points in Da Nang City to cultural heritage sites such as village temples, shrines, pagodas, and museums. We observed that cultural heritage sites and accommodations are concentrated along main roads in the city center, with additional 5-star resorts located further away. Public transportation stops and bike/motorbike rental points are mainly situated along the Han River. Therefore, we will propose utilizing low-emission or zero-carbon transportation options, such as cycling, engaging in activities with fishermen, motorbike tours, and exploring museum areas to promote environmental protection and enhance the tourist experience. This analysis aims to improve the rationality of location distribution and transportation convenience for tourists visiting cultural and historical sites in Da Nang's central area.

2. Brief of smart city technology

Manhattan methodology is used to assess the convenience level of transportation from lodging points and public transportation points to cultural and historical sites in Da Nang. It calculates the distance between amenities and reference points, with 1 grid unit representing 1 km. The convenience level is measured on a scale from 1 to 10, based on recommended distances for different transportation means. And then, average the scores to determine convenience indices for required travel distances. Based on these assessments, we can propose additional suitable locations for accommodations and public transportation on the city's traffic planning map.

Fig 1. Dividing grid cells using the Manhattan map

Fig 2. Rating scale of convenience

	km
10	0
9	1->2
8	2->3
7	3->4
6	4->5
5	5->6
4	6->7
3	7->8
2	8->9
1	>9

3. Anticipated Impact

Using the Manhattan map to evaluate the tourist convenience level visiting village temples and fisherman's shrines, have an index of 5.96 equivalent 4 -> 5 km. We do the same method

to evaluate the distribution of temple tourist attractions and museum attractions, and get the index of 8.56 and 8.43 respectively, equivalent 2 -> 3 km

Fig 3. Manhattan map analyzing village temples and fisherman's shrines

The convenience levels of transportation from accommodations to various cultural attractions by motorbikes, bicycles, and public transportation range from 2km to 4km (excluding walking). At present time, There are 5 main points serving residents and tourists in Danang City. Therefore, promoting sustainable transportation for residents and tourists, we will propose homestay accommodations at specific positions within the city (Fig.4), particularly at coordinates (22x28), (19x28), (21x29), and (22x29), where the heritage village temples of Hoa Lien and Hoa Ninh communes are located.

Fig 4. Map of proposed accommodation and public transportation points on the administrative map

4. Potential Challenges

One of the primary challenges associated with the implementation of the Manhattan method lies in its limited adoption for writing code or mathematical formulas in Excel. This lack of widespread utilization poses difficulties and obstacles, necessitating substantial investments of time, effort, and resources to successfully deploy and apply this method effectively. Overcoming these challenges entails overcoming the barriers of complexity and potentially incurring significant costs associated with the integration and implementation of the Manhattan method within Excel-based systems.

5. Collaboration opportunities

The Manhattan method is mainly based on writing code or algorithms on Excel software, which is the most basic part of the ArcGIS application. Therefore, using the ArcGIS application to design and propose urban and regional planning solutions becomes easier when users are proficient in using Excel algorithms.

Big Data Analytics for Enhancing Waste Management Systems in Smart Cities

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1. Project objectives

In the dynamic landscape of urbanization, the rise of smart cities has underscored the need for innovative waste management solutions. This paper focuses on leveraging big data to revolutionize waste management systems in smart cities. The primary objectives include analyzing existing challenges, exploring opportunities for big data integration, and assessing the economic and environmental impact of adopting intelligent waste management practices. By unlocking the potential of big data analytics, this research aims to propel urban centers toward sustainable and efficient waste management, offering a blueprint for future cities to thrive in harmony with their surroundings.

2. Brief Overview of Waste Management Systems in Smart Cities

In our smart city initiative, we have deployed cutting-edge technology to enhance various aspects of smart living, including waste management systems. We name this system DoNaBigData. Integrating technology and big data analytics in waste management helps cities optimize resource use, improve efficiency and promote city sustainability.

Figure 1. DoNaBigData System Overview

To ensure practicality and ensure that the system can handle continuous data processing and monitoring, we have proposed using the following technologies:

Sensor Integration and IoT Connectivity: smart waste bins equipped with sensors are deployed throughout the city to monitor waste levels in real-time. These sensors can detect when bins are full and waste categories are full, enabling exactly timely waste collection and preventing overflow. In addition, Internet of Things (IoT) devices connect the sensors to a centralized network, allowing seamless communication between waste bins and a control center.

In addition to building the real-time monitoring dashboard, our initiative harnesses predictive analytics for dynamic waste management. The data collected from sensors and IoT devices serves as a rich source for predictive analytics. Through the analysis of historical and real-time data patterns, our waste management system gains the ability to predict future trends in waste generation. This foresight empowers city officials to optimize waste collection routes, allocate resources more efficiently, and proactively address potential challenges in waste management.

Figure 2. Real-time monitoring dashboard of DoNaBigData System

Finally, with the data cleaned and analyzed, we build natural language processing models to make predictions about waste trends based on reports, which is also the basis for building waste trends. Build cross-platform applications for smart city users with alerts, tracking how waste is managed, classified, and processed.

3. Anticipated Impact

In essence, applying research and implementation of waste analysis management systems for smart cities will promise a holistic urban transformation, offering cleaner, greener, and cost-optimized cities and ultimately enhancing residents' quality of life. This is indicated with key impacts: efficient operations (real-time data analysis will optimize waste collection, reducing costs and ensuring quicker, more effective services for cleaner neighborhoods), environmental consciousness (informed by data insights, targeted recycling efforts will cut waste generation, fostering a community committed to sustainability), public awareness (Using the platforms that apply our data makes engaging communication channels will empower citizens with waste reduction knowledge, encouraging proactive community

participation), economic boost (beyond cost savings, the system opens revenue streams through recycling, attracting investment and enhancing economic vitality)

4. Potential Challenges

While our smart waste management system holds immense promise, acknowledging potential challenges is essential for a realistic evaluation of its implementation. Anticipating and addressing these challenges head-on will be crucial for the success of our innovation. Firstly, integrating the technology seamlessly into existing city infrastructure may require upgrades and careful coordination. Data security and privacy concerns, especially with handling sensitive information, necessitate robust cybersecurity measures to build public trust. Encouraging citizen adoption and engagement is vital, requiring effective communication strategies to overcome potential resistance or apathy. The initial implementation costs pose a financial challenge that requires convincing stakeholders of the long-term benefits. Navigating complex regulatory landscapes and obtaining approvals is time-consuming but crucial. Ensuring the skillset and training of personnel and overcoming resistance to change within organizations and among residents are key challenges. Lastly, adapting the system to diverse socio-economic and environmental conditions requires a tailored approach for different urban settings. Proactively addressing these challenges will enhance the success and resilience of our innovative waste management solution.

5. Collaboration opportunities

Unlocking the full potential of our smart waste management initiative requires strategic collaboration. We are actively seeking partnerships with leading technology providers and urban infrastructure experts to ensure seamless integration and scalability. Joining forces with cybersecurity specialists will fortify data security measures, instilling confidence in stakeholders. Collaborating with communication experts and community organizations will foster widespread citizen adoption and engagement. We are also open to collaboration with financial institutions and policymakers to secure the necessary support for the initial implementation costs and navigate regulatory challenges. Educational institutions are invited to join hands for skill development programs, ensuring a proficient workforce. Environmental organizations and experts are crucial collaborators to tailor our system for diverse urban landscapes. Through these strategic collaborations, we aim to propel our project to new heights, making a lasting impact on smart waste management in urban environments.

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IoT with Geostationary Satellite using S-Band

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1. Project objectives

In the next decade, our environment will use a massive number of connected objects to provide smart a ecosystem known as the Internet of Things (IoT). Many devices will be deployed in remote areas with limited access to terrestrial wireless networks and energy. This is where satellite connectivity provide the ability to connect any remote area. Recently, Low Power Wide area network has been demonstrated with Geostationary satellite using Echostar mobile network. In order to mitigate the power consumption and to achieve sufficient budget link, the maximum data rate is very limited low (100b/s). Considering the Echostar XXI radiofrequency performances in S-band, the LoRaWan uplink can be performed from 7dBm output power.

2. Miniature terminal connected to GEO satellite

Based on the Echostar mobile EM2050 module, our miniature 9*9*4cm board has demonstrated its capability to communicate in S-band with Geo satellites from Echostar mobile. The terminal is completely autonomous with the GNSS receiver to get the coordinates and synchronize the time. The device can send uplink and receive downlink from the GEO satellite. The terminal is extremely power efficient, enabling a lifetime higher than 3 years. Any type of sensor (inside or outside the waterproof casing) can be connected for various applications (water quality, soil moisture, fire detection ...). The terminal is low cost with a bill of material lower than 100\$ in low quantity volume.

Figure 1. Europe map of the GEO regional cells covered by Echo XXI. Continuous transmission to Echostar with 10dBm output power

3. Anticipated Impact

The project provides the capability to connect any sensor in a remote area with reduced power consumption. It is completely solving the well-known blind spot issue of terrestrial networks. The GEO satellite can connect any sensor in Europe with a continuous availability. This solution perfectly fits applications with short latency requirements. The use of low-power machine learning is the perfect match to extract from the raw data the useful piece of information which will be transmitted to the satellite.

Figure 2. Terminal board has demonstrated its capability to communicate in S-band with GEO satellite from Echostar mobile. The different modules in the terminal are presented in the right figure.

4. Potential Challenges

One of the key challenges with the Internet of Things project is the scaling with the robustness and data management which is out of our scope of expertise. Data provided from the terminal has to be correctly stored, analyzed and used. The availability of the Echostar mobile constellation is also a challenge with only Europe and US covered in the next years. The coverage limitation will be solved in the future with the deployment of a S-band LEO constellation for the rest of the world.

5. Collaboration opportunities

In collaboration with Echostar Mobile, Université Côte d’Azur has developed the terminal with AI features and GEO space connectivity. The technology is available and has been assessed in various environmental conditions up to tens of devices. We are looking for partners to scale up our experiments to larger areas with more sensors and usage of data.

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Connected Car For Real-Time Temperature (And Pollution) Mapping In ASEAN Cities

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1. Project objectives

As indicated by the title of a recent report from the World Bank, the cities in Southeast Asia have become 'unlivable' (Roberts et al., 2023). This situation is primarily due to the extreme temperatures that are observed in all countries of our region. For example, in April 2023, a record-breaking heat wave affected ASEAN countries, and several regional temperature records were set (44.2, 43.5, and 42.5 °C in Northern Vietnam, Luang Prabang and Vientiane, respectively). Furthermore, every climate model predicts a rise in the probability and frequency of heat waves, with the severity of these events expected to be highest in the Urban Heating Islands (UHI). Extremely high temperatures have a detrimental impact on people's health and can possibly result in death for the most vulnerable. This dangerous situation is reinforced by city air pollution, which often happens at the same time as UHI. This increased danger was already proven for PM2.5 pollution: "short-term exposure to extreme heat and [PM2.5] air pollution alone were individually associated with increased risk of mortality, but their co-exposure had larger effects beyond the sum of their individual effects (Rahman et al., 2022). To protect people, it is thus necessary to identify high-risk areas and consequently be able to **(i)** measure simultaneously the air temperature and the level of air pollution **(ii)** to make this measurements at the scale of a whole city; **(iii)** and to analyze and to interpret in 'real time' (at a scale of approximately 1 hour) this large amount data to finally be able **(iv)** to send warning messages to citizens and rescue teams as soon as a risk occurs.

Collecting and mapping city temperature using car sensors has already proven to be a feasible option (Marquès et al., 2022). Our project has the ambitious to go one step forward by installing devices measuring at the same time several air characteristics (temperature, moisture) and some of the dangerous pollutants, i.e. PM2.5, CO, NO₂, SO₂, ozone (Bălă, et al., 2021). At the same time air and pollution are measured, the location of the car will be collected by using the GPS position.

As pollution sensors are quite expensive and more challenging to run, we would like to use our previous project and experience in measuring air characteristic. Thus our project will start

by (i) producing and installing devices equipped with a GSP and able to collect air temperature & moisture (ii) transmitting these data to a server (iii) setting up an algorithm able to map the temperature (and the pollution later on) and send warning messages when a risk is detected. When we will have enough skills in these first steps, pollution sensors will be included.

2. Brief of smart city technology

Our project needs skills in 4 different aspects: (i) collecting data with accurate sensors, (ii) sending and storing the data, (iii) analysing and mapping the data and (iv) sending warning messages.

Accurate (and cheap) sensor will be installed on the roof of cars equipped with GPS to simultaneously collect and locate the data, in real time. The data will be sent to the gateway when the car is near-by and stored in a Lao database: "Kased Connect". Algorithms will show the trend and map of urban heat islands (and pollution location when we the cars will be equipped with such device). If the temperature and moisture reach a dangerous level, the last part of the project will consist in sending warning messages to citizens and rescue team. via the heat wave warning system.

3. Anticipated Impact

With a real-time monitoring system, it is possible to send a warning signal to the areas where the risk is increasing due to a temperature increase, a pollution increase, or both at the same time. The warning signal can be sent to individual people but also to different rescue teams. The individual people being informed and receiving at the same time recommendations on what to do to limit the risk for their health will have a higher probability of taking care and limiting the risk (staying at home to avoid pollution, drinking more water to cool down the body). The rescue team, being informed of a possible increase in the number of people coming to the hospital, will be more ready to take care of these people, preparing the necessary equipment to face any emergency situation. The impact should be a lower number of people having health problems and a lower stress level for the rescue team.

4. Potential Challenges

There are still several challenges before our innovation can be deployed on a large scale. Among them:

- recruit enough volunteers who are willing to install the sensors on their cars.
- having enough high locations to place a gateway and maximize its effectiveness.
- increase the volume of data that can be stored by Kased Connect
- calibration of the different sensors to provide a similar signal when in a similar environment and measure the uncertainty associated with our measures,
- have an algorithm efficient enough to send the warning signal only when there is a risk.

5. Collaboration opportunities

Collaboration is first necessary with our research team to benefit from their experience and not duplicate the work they have already done. This is the case for aspects related to electronics as well as computer science, data science, and statistics. Collaborations are also needed with government and city administrations to obtain permission to collect such large

amounts of data. Collaboration should also be found with the business sector to get their support for installing our devices on their cars. Finally our data should be sent to international data bases about air pollution from UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme).

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Smart Quality Robot To Assess Students Satisfaction and Assist Student Learning in STEM Education

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1. Project objectives

Under the escalating pressure for higher educational standards, today's learners aspire to elevate their academic proficiency. From training centers to universities, educational service providers relentlessly seek ways to enhance the quality of their services. Therefore, from training centers to universities, education service providers are constantly looking for ways to improve the quality of their training services. The emergence of groundbreaking technologies such as Machine Learning, IoT, and Big Data within the context of Industry 4.0 is fostering a powerful wave of transformation across all industries and services, with education notably among the sectors deeply influenced by this.

To leverage this potential and elevate educational quality, there have been numerous studies, technologies, and commercial products exploring the application of 4.0 Technologies 4.0 in the field of education. This ongoing applied research project is aimed to develop a Smart Quality Robot aimed to promote effective STEAM learning of the K-12 students. The Robot is designed for the purpose of evaluating learner satisfaction and providing feedback to instructors for more effective teaching. Simultaneously, the Robot aims to assist learners in achieving higher effectiveness in their learning process. The proposed intelligent robot is designed to perform functions of understanding and empathy, alongside monitoring students' learning activities to maximize their academic outcomes.

2. Brief of smart city technology

Understanding Learners: To accomplish this objective, technologies applied in Robot such as Face ID recognition, Facial expression recognition, and data interpretation. Employing these technologies, the robot autonomously navigates and observes learners, assessing their satisfaction and engagement during the learning process by analyzing facial expressions and other data. After each session, the robot automatically evaluates the outcomes and communicates feedback to the instructor, facilitating prompt adjustments for subsequent sessions and adapting across different learning sessions based on accumulated data.

Guiding Learners: During the learning process, learners can interact with the robot when they need to explore specific study areas or use different tools for practical exercises. The robot will listen and comprehend these requests, then guide learners to the relevant places, providing explanations as necessary. This interactive ability fosters a flexible and personalized learning experience, enhancing learners' understanding and comprehension throughout the learning process.

3. Anticipated Impact

The Robot is designed for use in a Maker Innovation Space serving learners to train on STEAM, and solve real-life problems.

At Maker Innovation Space, learners span a wide range, from K-12 students to college students. Each lesson is unique, necessitating various teaching methods such as theoretical instruction, practical exercises, experiential learning, and addressing real-world needs. This diversity in teaching methods requires the use of different tools and participation in numerous activities within the STEAM space. Educators are tasked with not only teaching but also guiding learners, comparing theory with practice, constructing models, conducting experiments, and testing. These multifaceted teaching and learning activities pose a complex challenge: how can we ensure learners stay engaged and follow along?

With these two objectives in mind, we anticipate that a Smart Quality Robot will effectively accomplish the task of assessing learner satisfaction. This not only saves time and effort in enhancing the quality of teaching but also provides service providers with a clearer understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of their teaching process. It creates opportunities to implement more effective teaching methods, grounded in accurate feedback from learners. This not only

Robotic Solution

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1. Project objectives

Abstract: This paper explores a Smart solution of integrating robotics and artificial intelligence (AI), emphasizing improvements in overall human life quality. Leveraging high-end technology , our project successfully developed a prototype that combines a Scara robo with Machine Learning. Our research demonstrates effective methods in multiple fields.

Keywords: Scarda robot, robotics, AI

Introduction: With the advancement of robotics and AI, the integration of these technologies into everyday life has become a significant focus of research and urban management. This paper aims to explore applications related to robots and object detection models in the fields of agriculture and medicine, highlighting the potential of this integration to automate conventional tasks in these domains.

2. Brief of smart city technology

Methodology:

- *Objective Definition:* Define academic objectives centered on integrating robotics and Machine Learning for precision automation in agriculture and medical applications.
- *Technology Selection:* Choose suitable technologies, including Scara robot and machine learning, computer vision applied to a wide range of objects for the project.
- *Setup and Design:* Acquire hardware, set up software, and design 3D model for Scara robot and caculate the inverse kinematics.
- *Model Development and Integration:* Develop an object detection model for increase the range of objects and seamlessly integrate it with the Scara robot.

Technology:

Computer Vision: Leveraging AI algorithms, the project analyzes visual data from the robot's cameras to recognize objects based on predefined patterns. Employing image processing, it calculates object coordinates in the robot's field and transmits them to the control system. This dynamic integration enables the robot to adjust movements and interactions based on the received spatial information, enhancing its adaptability and cognitive capabilities.

Robotic: Utilizing robots to automate traditional daily tasks, we have opted for the Scara robot due to its notable stability and flexibility. The inclusion of a gripper and vacuum suction cup further enhances the robot's versatility, allowing it to proficiently execute a variety of tasks in diverse settings. This strategic combination enables the robot to contribute significantly to automating routine human activities, streamlining processes, and increasing overall efficiency in daily life.

3. Anticipated Impact

Results: Our paper showcase the development of an integrated solution featuring a 4-degree-of-freedom Scara Robot controlled by inverse kinematics equations and complemented by Machine Learning. The Scara Robot's design and control mechanism have exhibited notable flexibility and precision. The system's efficacy has been validated through practical applications in tomato harvesting and assisting patients with routine works.

4. Potential Challenges

Technical Limitations: Acknowledge technical constraints, such as relating to system reliability and adaptability to different environments.

Long-term Sustainability: Discuss potential environmental impact and resource consumption, considering the long-term sustainability of these technologies.

5. Collaboration opportunities

International Collaboration: Explore opportunities for collaboration on a global scale. Engage with researchers, organizations, and institutions from different countries to share insights, data, and expertise.

Academic Partnerships: Collaborate with academic institutions to leverage diverse expertise in robotics, AI, agriculture, and medicine. Engage in joint research projects, share resources, and benefit from interdisciplinary perspectives.

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Determination of Pol Content in Molasses Using Near-Infrared Spectroscopy and Partial Least Squares Regression

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1. Project objectives

The determination of Pol in molasses is pivotal for quality assurance and detecting potential adulteration. Furthermore, Pol measurements at various processing stages enable the monitoring of operational efficiency, permitting prompt adjustments to maintain overall product quality. Traditionally, the analysis using instruments like a polarimeter can be complex and time-consuming. However, the integration of Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIR) provides a rapid and efficient alternative. NIR spectroscopy allows for real-time, non-destructive and simultaneous assessment of molecular composition without the need for extensive sample preparation. The aim of this project is to build a non-destructive method based on NIR spectra combined with PLS regression to determine Pol content in sugar cane molasses.

2. Brief of the Regression Method

Twenty (20) samples of sugar cane molasses are packaged in dark 10-liter cans, transported from Lam Son sugar cane factory to the laboratory at Hanoi University of Science and Technology. Upon receipt, each sample is transferred to a convenient 500ml bottle for ease of handling during research. The method for determining the Polarity content in molasses begins by diluting it at a 60°C. Next, 1g of lead acetate is added, stirred thoroughly, and then approximately 10-20ml of the first filtrate is carefully discarded. Use distilled water to calibrate the Polarimeter and then measure the prepared solution. This process is repeated three times, and the average result is used to accurately determine the Pol content, ensuring the reliability of the measurement method.

Initially, the raw spectra undergo preprocessing utilizing diverse methods such as multiplicative scatter correction (MSC), standard normal variate (SNV), and first and second

derivative Savitzky–Golay (SG). These methods aim to eliminate variations in slope and correct scattering effects. Subsequently, the samples are randomly divided into two sets: a calibration set, constituting 70% for model building, and a prediction set, comprising 30% for predictive purposes. The spectral data are then linked to Pol content through a Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression model. The models' performance is validated through cross-validation (5 Kfold) and assessed using statistical parameters, including the coefficient of determination (R^2) between measured and predicted values and the mean square error (MSE) of datasets.

The optimal model, utilizing SG preprocessed spectra with window length, polyorder, and derivative set at 15, 2, 0, respectively, achieved calibration and prediction set accuracies of 0.843 and 0.860. This result shows that the combination of NIR spectroscopy and PLS regression is a rapid method for determining Pol content in molasses.

3. Anticipated Impact

The impact of this study is to provide a rapid method for the quantitative determination of the Pol degree of molasses using a portable NIR spectrometer. The application of fast, non-destructive, and real-time prediction methods is beneficial for the quality monitoring process in the sugar industry and contributes to economic benefits and human health protection.

4. Potential Challenges

Although this result is promising, further research and development are still needed to obtain a more robust calibration model based on multiple molasses bases from different companies, origins, etc.

5. Collaboration opportunities

Sugar companies can collaborate to diversify molasses samples for a more effective modeling to determine Pol content, while technology companies can assist in establishing a comprehensive monitoring system across the entire chain during the sugarcane production process.

6. Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Ministry of Science and Technology of Vietnam in the project “Application of quick analysis methods combining multi-dimensional data processing and machine learning in quality control of some types of seafood” (No: ĐTĐL.CN-33/20).

IoT System For Safety Monitoring And Early Warning Of Tourists Using The Lorawan Network

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1. Project objectives

In this project, the main contribution lies in the successful deployment and integration of IoT technologies to ensure beach safety. The most important results achieved are smart sensor integration, LoRa connectivity, and integration with the Web/Apps platform.

2. Brief of technology

When the system is powered from the Battery block, the sensor module blocks will read values from the environment and send them to the central processing block to process the data. Next, the data will be fed into the LoRa module by the main processing block. Data from the LoRa module block will continue to be transmitted to the Gateway block by the LoRa network. Then the data will be sent to the LoRaWAN Server through the Gateway. Here, data will be stored and users need to install an app or web to observe the transmitted sensor values. Warning signals will be generated at the Blynk IoT app and sent to the device user as well as the supervisor through two methods: email and notification on the app.

Figure 1. System block diagram

Figure 2: Algorithm and demo prototype

3. Anticipated Impact

The implementation of an IoT system utilizing LoRaWAN technology for safety monitoring in tourism will revolutionize early warnings, enabling real-time alerts and precise location tracking, drastically enhancing tourist safety and optimizing emergency response, thereby redefining the tourism experience. Ultimately, this innovation promises to create a safer, more secure environment for tourists while bolstering the efficiency of local emergency services.

4. Potential Challenges

The implementation of an IoT system for safety monitoring in tourism using LoRaWAN may face challenges such as ensuring comprehensive network coverage in remote areas, managing data privacy and security concerns associated with sensitive tourist information, and navigating regulatory compliance across different regions or countries, potentially impacting the scalability and seamless operation of the system.

5. Collaboration opportunities

The project presents collaboration opportunities with local tourism authorities, emergency services, and technology firms to establish standardized safety protocols, integrate the IoT system with existing infrastructure, and conduct joint research to continually enhance safety measures. Additionally, partnerships with academic institutions could foster innovation, allowing for continuous improvement and the development of best practices in IoT-based tourist safety.

Effective Integration Of Neural Network And skin Spectroscopy In Diagnosing Skin Conditions

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1. Project objectives

Among the various pressing desires for improved quality of life, there exists a pronounced and growing demand for dermatological treatment and diagnostic services. However many diagnosis approaches that are commonly employed are expensive, time-consuming, and invasive. Therefore, there's a profound need for a convenient and quick skin diagnosis method.

The rapid evolution of Artificial Intelligence has paved the way to a variety of computer-aided solutions in many fields including medical. Thus, we propose an alternative approach to diagnosing skin conditions that are based on Neural Network and skin spectroscopy. We aim to integrate these models into a novel application that can be used to quickly diagnose the conditions of the skin. This is intended to be used by both the general people and experts who require convenient diagnosis methods.

2. Implementation of Neural Network models for skin health diagnosis

The implementation is explained in Figure 1. The skin database contains the optical properties of a variety of human skin. This database is used to train Neural Network models to diagnose the conditions of the skin. Specifically, the models are used to predict the concentration of various skin components. These concentrations are next used to predict the conditions of the skin. Thus, by providing spectroscopic data, the user can quickly diagnose their skin conditions. This allows for a quick and easy way to diagnose the conditions of the skin.

Figure 1. Implementation of Neural Network models in predicting skin conditions.

3. Anticipated Impact

The proposed diagnosis method can be used to quickly and effectively diagnose various skin conditions. This would improve the quality of life of the people, and help ease the burden on the healthcare system. Having a quick and convenient diagnosis method would also help people quickly realize their skin conditions and diseases, and seek medical attention when needed. The diagnoses can also be saved on cloud computing infrastructure, allowing for easy monitoring and analysis.

4. Potential Challenges

The skin is the complex organ of the human body, and it differs greatly from person to person. There are various skin types, characterized by different skin tones, structures, conditions, and skin areas. Therefore, the skin database used in our approach needs to be extremely robust and diverse to accurately predict various skin conditions. Additionally, skin spectroscopy also requires specialized equipment.

5. Collaboration opportunities

The success of this proposal largely depends on the following collaboration opportunities: medical facilities, universities, IT companies.

Collaboration with medical facilities is crucial to the development of our approach. They would help us understand the skin structure and its conditions, gather data on human skin and accurately validate the results and effectiveness of our system. The knowledge of skin structure and spectroscopy lays the foundation of our system.

The help of universities and IT companies would be tremendous in the development and deployment of our system. Our ability to scale relies on the development of the Neural Network models and performance of the computing infrastructure, thus making universities and IT companies the ideal partners.

SMART LIBRARY

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1. Smart Library objectives

The integration of a Smart Library heralds a novel paradigm in the conventional applications inherent to the city of Danang.

Link: <https://smartlibrary.azurewebsites.net/>

Abstract: Smart library mainly embarks on a nuanced exploration of the symbiotic integration of IoT into conventional practices, specifically within the library setting. The imperative is centered around efficient management and resource conservation, with a particular focus on innovation and technology adoption.

Keywords: Smart Library, Library in Smart City, IOT in Library

Introduction: The prevailing operational approaches in Danang's libraries adhere to traditional methods. This scholarly article aims to contribute significantly by proposing a technologically advanced solution for library services, fostering Danang city development.

2. Technologies in Smart Library

Methodology: Our methodology involves the research and development of an advanced library system utilizing high-end technologies, including IoT, LoRa network, databases, data science, and machine learning. This aims to automate librarian tasks and improve traditional library services. The approach ensures seamless integration of these technologies to optimize workflows and enhance overall service efficiency.

ML/AI Technology: Our integrated website leverages Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies to streamline librarian operations and enhance data science capabilities. This results in informed decision-making and strategic advertising recommendations, ultimately optimizing the user experience by reducing the time spent in finding suitable books.

IoT/Lora Technology: With our system, the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) and AI enhances the capabilities of the smart library. By utilizing cameras and sensors, the library can automatically scan QR codes on books and recognize human faces, thereby potentially saving manpower and enhancing security. Moreover, with the support of the LoRa system, user data and activities can be tracked and seamlessly sent to the database.

WebServer/Database: Smart city platform offers online services, streamlining the collection and secure storage of customer information in a database. Librarians, equipped with this platform, can effectively manage user data, enhancing both efficiency and security. Users are provided with various methods for borrowing and returning books.

3. Results & Impacts

Results: The deployment of our smart library anticipates significant improvements in the quality of life through the implementation of advanced technologies and smart systems.

Users: Our smart library system's hardware is finished, allowing users to borrow and return books 75% faster than traditional methods. Equipped with biometric security like fingerprint and facial recognition, the system ensures information security. Users can also use the website to effectively search for books and receive personalized recommendations, saving significant search time.

Librarians: Our Smart Library comprises an integrated management system with a robust database infrastructure. The automation of book borrowing and return processes serves to optimize operational workflows and human resource utilization. Moreover, the automatic collection of user data significantly mitigates the occurrence of errors in the management process.

Discussion: Smart libraries, empowered by AI and IoT, redefine the library experience with automated services and personalized features. Challenges include data security and digital literacy. Despite obstacles, smart libraries contribute to a more connected and advanced learning environment in the development of Danang City.

4. Potential Challenges

- Introducing new technologies to library patrons and staff may face resistance. Therefore, training programs and robust support for users and staff are crucial.
- The adoption of smart technologies involves significant upfront costs for hardware, software, and ongoing maintenance.

5. Collaboration opportunities

Smart libraries have ample collaboration opportunities to enhance services and community engagement.

- ✓ **Professional Associations:** Engaging with libraries in Danang City and information science associations provides a platform for knowledge exchange, collaborative research, and networking with professionals in the field.
- ✓ **Educational Institutions:** Collaborating with schools, colleges, and universities allows smart libraries to enrich academic resources, offer specialized programs, and support research initiatives, fostering a seamless flow of information and resources.

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Application of Low-Power Embedded Devices in Water Meter Digit Recognition

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1. Project objectives

The objective of this project is to explore and implement the application of low-power embedded devices for accurate and efficient recognition of digits in water meters. The aim is to develop a robust system that utilizes embedded technology to reliably identify and interpret meter readings, contributing to enhanced monitoring and management of water consumption.

2. Brief of technology

The technology employed in this project revolves around low-power embedded devices, leveraging their capabilities in image processing, machine learning algorithms, and sensor integration. These devices are equipped with specialized hardware and software components tailored for efficient and accurate recognition of digits within water meter displays. Image sensors capture the meter readings, and the embedded systems process this visual data using image processing techniques. Machine learning algorithms are employed to analyze and interpret the digits, enabling the system to recognize and extract numerical values. Additionally, these embedded devices are designed for low power consumption, ensuring prolonged operation without frequent battery replacements. The combination of these technologies facilitates a reliable and energy-efficient solution for water meter digit recognition, enhancing monitoring and management capabilities.

Figure 1. System block diagram

```
1/1 [=====] - 0s 42ms/step
Gia tri du doan: 4
1/1 [=====] - 0s 29ms/step
Gia tri du doan: 3
1/1 [=====] - 0s 35ms/step
Gia tri du doan: 8b
1/1 [=====] - 0s 25ms/step
Gia tri du doan: 5
1/1 [=====] - 0s 27ms/step
Gia tri du doan: 8a
```

img_1	img_2	img_3	img_4	img_5

Figure 2: capture image from water meter and prediction results.

3. Anticipated Impact

The project's implementation of low-power embedded devices for water meter digit recognition anticipates enhancing data accuracy and accessibility, fostering informed decision-making while promoting resource efficiency. This initiative aims to streamline meter reading processes, empowering utilities and consumers with precise, real-time water usage information for improved conservation efforts.

4. Potential Challenges

Integrating low-power embedded devices for water meter digit recognition may encounter challenges in ensuring consistent accuracy across diverse meter designs and conditions, alongside addressing data security concerns for sensitive consumption information. Sustaining device reliability in various environmental settings also poses ongoing operational hurdles for long-term implementation.

5. Collaboration opportunities

This project presents collaboration opportunities with technology firms for device optimization and utility companies for field testing and implementation, fostering potential partnerships with academic institutions for algorithm refinement and regulatory bodies for compliance assurance. Engagement with environmental organizations can leverage data insights for sustainable water management, while involvement with consumer groups ensures user-friendly interfaces and privacy considerations are addressed.

Using Lorawan To Monitor Power System Quality In Real-Time

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1. Project objectives

Currently, at the Chu Puh substation, there are 47 manually controlled capacitor banks, posing challenges to grid synchronization and power quality. These reactive power compensation stations are manually operated, monitored, and checked according to predetermined schedules, making them unable to detect abnormalities such as damaged capacitor arrays or faulty capacitor switching devices. These issues have adversely impacted power quality, particularly causing power loss. The development of an integrated IoT system to monitor power quality and real-time control of low-voltage capacitor control stations is the subject of this research. However, existing IoT systems are unable to ensure transmission in areas without network connectivity or with weak or lost signals. The team has designed an IoT system incorporating LoraWan communication to ensure uninterrupted data transmission and prevent data loss. By combining data collection units with LoraWan communication, data from the stations will be sent to a gateway within the area to push data to the database, unaffected by signal-related issues.

2. Brief of smart city technology

Our team took on the task of developing a solution dubbed "Using LoraWan to monitor power system quality in real-time."

This groundbreaking project comprises two primary components: the data logger and the gateway. The data loggers serve a crucial function by meticulously reading and monitoring power

parameters, extracting data from the Ducati R8 system, and overseeing the physical operation of the contactors within the capacitor bank's switching control system. During periods of stable signal connectivity, these data loggers autonomously push gathered information directly into the database, ensuring a continuous flow of real-time data updates.

However, acknowledging the unpredictability of signal integrity in certain areas, the system has been intelligently designed to seamlessly switch to the LoraWan network communication for data transmission to strategically positioned gateway stations in order to ensure uninterrupted and reliable data transmission, irrespective of signal-related challenges.

Should any issues arise within the transmission system, immediate alerts are dispatched to the monitoring web platform and mobile application and sent via SMS to the administrator, enabling prompt and efficient troubleshooting, mitigating potential disruptions or faults.

3. Anticipated Impact

When the data loggers and gateway stations are successfully installed across all transmission stations and capacitor banks, they will provide comprehensive monitoring for the current electrical transmission system. This implementation aims to ensure the minimization of reactive power losses and prompt detection of any irregularities or anomalies. Furthermore, the integration of LoraWan technology fortifies the surveillance system, imparting resilience against signal-related disruptions. This strategic amalgamation guarantees the system's functionality across diverse terrains and under varying environmental conditions, ensuring reliable and uninterrupted data transmission. The implementation is poised to revolutionize the existing monitoring protocols, ensuring the seamless operation of power systems, regardless of geographical constraints or signal interferences.

4. Potential Challenges

With current technology, LoRa transmission still faces significant distance limitations. Therefore, additional communication networks like mesh networks may be required. The number of nodes transmitting to the gateway is restricted due to limited synchronization in transmission. Moreover, managing multiple devices demands a substantial management system with extensive data storage, surpassing the capacities of current databases. Hardware limitations also pose challenges in ensuring continuous and prolonged operation. These limitations underscore the necessity for innovative solutions and technological advancements to harness the full potential of IoT systems in power management.

5. Collaboration opportunities

To strengthen or scale the project, the team searched for methods and planned to focus on a number of specific areas such as:

1. Technology: integrating AIoT technology. With the collected data, AI technology can be used to analyze and predict system operating conditions as well as take early action on abnormalities in transmission system data.
2. Market Research: Regularly collect and analyze feedback from users to identify areas for improvement and new features that can be developed. Additionally, the team continuously monitors competitor updates and market trends to make informed decisions.
3. Cooperation: Cooperate with other businesses or startups to take advantage of common resources. Build direct relationships with EVN managers and partners in the electricity industry.
4. Attract Investors: Develop a coherent strategy to make your project attractive, attracting investors to secure additional capital for expansion goals.

A LoRaWAN-based system for water-parameters monitoring in shrimp farm

by [Hai-Phong Phan*, Nguyen-Bao Nguyen Phan, Thi-Kieu Tran, Nhat-Quang Nguyen Duc, Hue University of Sciences (*phongph@husc.edu.vn)]

1. Project objectives

The water environment parameters in the shrimp farm pond are crucial for the success of the breeding. The quality and survival of the shrimp depend on many environmental factors in the pond. If the farmer does not act quickly when a parameter worsens, it can cause large-scale shrimp mortality and negative impacts on the breeding season.

Among many water parameters that affect the shrimp farming process, pH, DO and ORP are important parameters and need to be measured several times a day. Therefore, in this project, we focus on building an IoT system to monitor three main parameters of a shrimp pond: pH, ORP, and DO. The system needs to automatically measure these parameters at multiple times of the day and send data back to the farmer through wireless networks. We chose the LoRaWAN network to deploy the system because of its ability to connect wirelessly over long distances, and low power consumption suitable for the measurement points of shrimp ponds located in a large area that conventional wireless networks cannot meet.

2. LoRa technology

LoRa is a radio modulation technology for low-power, wide area networks (LPWANs). The modulation method is proposed by Semtech to provide effective wireless communication for IoT devices. The LoRa technology can provide long-range wireless communication: up to 5 kilometers in urban areas, and up to 15 kilometers or more in rural areas (line of sight).

Basically, the model of an IoT system based on LoRaWAN will be given in the figure below.

In the proposed model, the End Nodes gather environmental data and transmit it to the gateways via LoRa connection. The End Node is equipped with a lithium battery and can be recharged using a solar panel. As a result, it can operate autonomously without relying on a power supplier.

Some pictures of the sensor, the End Node and user interface are shown as in below.

3. Anticipated Impact

The deployment of the project is expected to significantly improve the quality of life for shrimp farmers. By providing real-time, accurate data on the crucial parameters, farmers can make informed decisions about their farming practices. This could lead to increased shrimp survival rates, higher yields, and ultimately, increased income for the farmers. Additionally, the use of LoRaWAN technology could pave the way for more widespread use of IoT in agriculture, leading to more efficient and sustainable farming practices overall.

4. Potential Challenges

Some potential challenges that may arise include ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the sensors used to measure water parameters. Additionally, the system must be robust enough to withstand the harsh conditions of a shrimp pond. There may also be challenges related to the installation and maintenance of the system, especially in remote or difficult-to-reach locations. Finally, there could be challenges related to data security and privacy, as the system involves the transmission of data over a wireless network.

5. Collaboration opportunities

To strengthen or scale this project, we could look for partnerships with technology companies specializing in IoT or LoRaWAN. They could provide technical expertise and resources to help improve the system. Besides, collaborations with universities or research institutions could provide valuable insights into the most effective ways to monitor and maintain water quality in shrimp ponds. Finally, partnerships with local governments or agricultural organizations could help to promote the system among shrimp farmers and provide funding or other resources for its implementation.

LoRaTrack Logistics

Tracking and Managing Smart Containers in the Supply Chain - Utilizing LoRaWAN

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1. Project objectives

In the context of the integration of the international market and the globalization of economic activities, the landscape of international trade is undergoing remarkable transformation. Notably, sea transport accounts for over 80% of the global trade volume; however, this mode of transportation is fraught with substantial risks. The World Shipping Council's 2022 report indicates an annual average loss of 1629 containers at sea, highlighting the pronounced challenges inherent in maritime trade.

This project aims to establish a container monitoring system within the port, transforming ordinary containers into smart ones. Through the incorporation of IoT technologies, sensors, real-time GPS tracking, and Lora communication, these smart containers attain the capability to furnish comprehensive data.

The project's objective is to collect real-time data from the containers through sensors, evaluating and analyzing this information to generate timely notifications for management personnel, enabling swift issue resolution. The project focuses on monitoring various aspects of containers, including temperature, humidity, GPS location, detecting vibrations, and determining whether the container doors are open or closed.

2. Brief of smart city technology

The project involves the integration of various devices into a comprehensive system, as depicted in Figure 1. This system consists of three key components: the node block, the gateway block, and the master block. These blocks are interconnected through LoRa technology. The choice of LoRa technology brings numerous advantages, notably extended coverage and low power consumption. With its low power consumption, we have incorporated the use of sustainable energy, specifically solar energy, enabling the system to operate independently. This approach avoids the use of electrical wires, reducing the risk of fire hazards in the port and preserving the natural environment.

The node blocks are devices installed on containers, integrated with sensors for container monitoring. GPS technology on the node block is utilized for pinpointing the container's

location within the port. Additionally, we have integrated acceleration sensors within the container to detect vibrations affecting the container, track the position in case of GPS signal loss, and determine the open or closed status of the container doors.

Figure 1. System design

After data is transmitted to the Master through the gateway from the node block, it is optimized to be sent to the cloud. This process allows supervisors to analyze and evaluate the data promptly, making informed decisions to ensure efficient cargo transportation.

3. Anticipated Impact

The implementation of the Tracking and Managing Smart Containers system using LoRaWAN is expected to:

- Improve operational efficiency in seaports by providing real-time data on container status, location, and environmental conditions. This enhanced visibility is likely to streamline logistics, reduce delays, and improve overall supply chain efficiency.
- Bring cost-effectiveness through extended coverage and low power consumption, promoting a sustainable solution. The system's ability to generate immediate alerts during incidents contributes to effective crisis management, minimizing potential losses in transportation disputes.

Overall, adopting this system is anticipated to bring positive impacts to the maritime industry, including operational efficiency gains, cost-effectiveness, and enhanced risk management capabilities.

4. Potential Challenges

This is a complex system made up of different parts, requiring a skilled team with advanced technical knowledge and devices that guarantee strong performance. Following rules about data and privacy might be difficult when setting up this project.

The project involves putting LoRa sensors on containers, creating a LoRa network, and making software to manage data. These jobs might cost a lot and take a long time to finish.

5. Collaboration opportunities

Technical Collaboration: Collaborate with companies or technical partners experienced in hardware and software design in the IoT and LoRa field to jointly develop the project.

Collaboration with Ports and Logistics Enterprises: Work closely with ports and logistics enterprises to implement the model in practice, assessing effectiveness and operational processes. This will lead to appropriate adjustments based on practical needs and the development of a comprehensive system.

Leakage detection and location in the pipeline system using LPV observer via LORA Network

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1. Project objectives

The pipeline system is of paramount importance to transport water, oil, and others. According to the International Water Services Association (IWSA), water losses vary between 8% and 24% in developed countries and 25–45% in developing countries. Therefore, leakage detection and location plays a vital role in saving the economy, natural resources, and environment. Many methods for leakage detection such as signal analysis-based approach and model-based methods.

The key requirements for leakage detection in the pipeline system are: to use on-board sensors equipped to measure the intake and offtake pressure and massflow of the pipeline; to utilize a Wireless Sensor Network-Based Infrastructure (such as LoRa or 4G network) to transmit the collected data from the pipeline system to monitoring center; to minimize the effect of sensor noises and system uncertainties in order to detect the leakage in near real-time.

The main objective of this project is to design the LPV observer in order to detect and localize the leakage in the pipeline system using intake and offtake pressure and flow data of the pipeline system that are collected via a Wireless LoRa network. This approach aims at enhancing accuracy, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness in leakage detection and location and at transforming the proposed method to a real-life system.

2. Brief of smart city technology

In this project, a Wireless LoRa Sensor Network-Based Infrastructure is designed for leakage detection and location in the pipeline system. The structure and the test bench of proposed system is shown in Figure 1

Figure 1: UTE-WATACO test bench : the structure of the system (left), the real test bench (right)

The main algorithm to detect and localize the leakage in the pipeline system is based on the robust Linear Parameter Varying (LPV) observer, whose inputs and outputs are the intake and offtake pressure and massflow, respectively. The output of the proposed observer is the leakage location.

The structure of LPV observer is as follows: $\hat{\dot{x}} = A(\rho)\hat{x} + B(\rho)u + L(\rho)(y - C\hat{x})$

where $\hat{x}$ is estimated state vector (including leakage location); $A(\rho)$, $B(\rho)$, and C are known; y and u are measured through sensors.

The observer matrix $L(\rho)$ will be designed by using a polytopic method to solve the Linear Matrix Inequalities.

The results of leakage detection in the real-time domain are displayed on the WinCC monitoring interface in the following Figure 2.

Figure 2: The WinCC user interface in the experimental scenario.

3. Anticipated Impact

The deployment of this project, integrating a Wireless LoRa Sensor Network-Based Infrastructure and an observer for leak detection in pipelines, promises an impact on urban life.

1. Environmental Conservation: Rapid leak identification reduces water loss, preserving resources and mitigating environmental pollution, contributing to a healthier urban ecosystem.
2. Resource Optimization: Efficient pipeline system management minimizes losses, optimizing resource utilization and ensuring a consistent supply of resources for residents.
3. Smart City Advancement: Embracing cutting-edge technology aligns with smart city goals, fostering efficient infrastructure management and improving urban living standards.

4. Potential Challenges

The innovation of the project using a Wireless LoRa Sensors Network and a robust LPV observer for leak detection and location faces several potential challenges: Data transmission delay, privacy and data security concerns, effect of uncertainties, and cost considerations.

Addressing these challenges requires meticulous planning and collaborative efforts to ensure successful and sustainable implementation of the project in urban infrastructure.

5. Collaboration opportunities

In order to improve and scale up our pipeline monitoring system project, we seek collaborations in various areas:

1. Research Collaboration: Improve the Wireless LoRa Sensors Network, and develop a novel approach to estimate the leakage location considering time delay and uncertainties.
2. Industry Collaboration: Implement the proposed approach to a real life pipeline system.
3. Funding Partnerships: Seek investors for scaling efforts.

Collaboration in these areas will fortify our project, enabling scalability and real-world effectiveness while enhancing urban infrastructure and quality of life.

Develop a Fire and Explosion prevention system for parking and basement on LoRaWAN platform

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1. Project objectives

The goal of the project is to research and propose solutions to improve the effectiveness of fire prevention and suppression in parking lots. The following conditions must be met by the following requirements:

- Minimizing the risk of fire and explosion.
- Improving the capacity to respond and extinguish fires when they occur.
- Ensuring safety for people and property.

2. Brief of smart city technology

2.1. Gas sensor

The sensor will detect combustible substance leaks such as gasoline and fuel. When the sensor detects that the amount of flammable gas, exceeds the safety threshold, it can trigger the fire suppression system, which will deploy the corresponding fire suppression measures.

2.2. Temperature sensor

The sensor detects anomalous temperature increases in the fire zone. When the temperature reaches a dangerous level, this sensor may transmit a warning to everyone to check and prevent, as well as trigger the fire suppression system, which will deploy firefighting measures such as spraying fire extinguishers or water spray.

2.3. Infrared sensor

When infrared rays appear, the light will switch on, allowing individuals to move in the garage more safely.

2.4. LCD

Lcd is used to display temperature, humidity, gas and related information.

3. Anticipated Impact

Minimize the risk of fire and explosion: Implementing fire prevention and fighting measures in accordance/ compliance with regulations helps detect and promptly prevent fire and explosion risks, limiting property and life loss.

Ensuring safety for people and property: Fire prevention and fighting in the parking lot area helps protect the safety of people and property in the parking lot, preventing serious consequences caused by fire and explosion.

Improve the ability to respond and extinguish fires when they occur: The fire protection system at the parking lot helps people and firemen in swiftly detecting, responding to, and extinguishing fires, minimizing damage.

4. Potential Challenges

- Large scale of implementation.
- People's fire prevention awareness.
- High implementation costs.

5. Collaboration opportunities

We hope to find developers and investors so that the system can be completed and equipped in many parking lots

Low-cost system LoRaWAN Network for Fire Monitoring in Campus – LoraWAN4FM

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1. Project objectives

In University's buildings, especially in narrow spaces with many equipment such as laboratories, the risk of fire or toxic gas density is always present, as the consequences of these fires expand beyond the destruction of the ecosystem. Autonomously, remote solutions for early fire detection should be developed in combination with an early fire warning system such as smoke or gas sensors equipped in a building management system (BMS). Internet of Things (IoT) is a fast-growing technology. It includes equipment, buildings, electrical systems, and everyday things with computing and sensing capabilities. These objects can be managed and monitored remotely as they are connected to the Internet. The assessment of the fire risk of an area and the communication of this fact to the population could reduce the number of fires originated by accident or due to the carelessness of the users. In this project, we design and implement a low-cost prototype system LoRaWAN-based system for smart building fire detection and anticipated presence of a fire in sensible working areas. The system is comprised of several LoRa nodes with sensors to collect the real-time data like temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and CO₂ of the environment. The data from the nodes is stored and processed in a The Things Network server that sends the data to a website for the graphic visualization of the collected data. The prototype is tested in a real environment and, the results show that it is possible to cover a circular area of a radius of 500m with a single LoraWan gateway installed on the University building's rooftop.

2. Brief of smart city technology

The prototype system is based on LoRa technology, i.e., the network topology used in this project will be an infrastructure architecture where a LoRaWan gateway will be in charge of collecting data from nodes and, several nodes will be spread along within the scenario. The node is in charge of gathering data from the environment through the different used sensors (temperature, eCO₂, TVOC, humidity, wind speed...etc). The collected data will be stored in a network storage server. In this case, an already developed service provided by The Things Network was used. Finally, a web application will be the user's interface to visualize the data from sensors and provide the estimated information of warning areas. Figure 1 shows the

network architecture of our proposal. IoT enabled fire detection system aimed at enhancing early warning capabilities and improving emergency response in various environments. Leveraging the interconnected nature of IoT devices and the advantages of Lora protocol, the proposed system integrates a network of smart sensors strategically placed to detect key indicators of fire, including smoke, heat, and flame. The sensors transmit real-time data to a centralized cloud-based platform, where advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms analyze the information for accurate and timely fire detection. The proposed system provides an additional efficient solution for BMS system. Figure 2 shows an example of data collection recorded by the node.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 1: LoraWAN4FM system topology based on LoRa technology. Figure 2: Data visualization on user's interface (CO2; TVOC)

3. Anticipated Impact

The system can be integrated into Building/Campus Management System (BMS) so that it can help the university manager catch up on information about the real-time environmental databases in some sensible area like laboratories, car parking. Managers may issue a number of solutions for integrating with building energy consumption management, analyzing and managing working conditions in special areas on university campus. Thanks to that, the development of a comprehensive "smart campus" solution will be implemented.

4. Potential Challenges

There could be a number of difficulties:

- Hardware design: how to choose the best sensors with high-quality (precision; best resolution) and adaptive with the system LoraWan gateway and its communication protocol.
- Data access: risk of an internet connection failure in buildings
- Algorithm development to produce a reliable output: Creating a deep learning model is a difficult task. It is obvious that the development process will necessitate a significant amount of human labor and data exploration.
- Improving data transmission quality with extremely hot temperatures. As a result, a decision of fire detection can be made with very low data transmission quality based on extremely hot temperatures.

5. Collaboration opportunities

The system can be scalable and able to multitask, such as recognizing air quality the room, detecting early cause of fire, etc. There will be a collaboration among BMS and IT research units to provide fire or air-quality standard indexes which lead to more accurate data analysis

and data classification. As a result, the commercialization of this prototype device can be supported by the stakeholder.

Autonomous Garbage Collecting Robot using Path Planning Algorithm and LoRa Network

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1. Project objectives

The primary objective of this project is to develop an efficient robot capable of autonomously navigating and collecting garbage. By leveraging advanced path planning algorithms, the robot will efficiently navigate through various environments, ensuring thorough and effective waste collection. Additionally, the integration of LoRa network technology aims to enhance remote communication capabilities, allowing for real-time monitoring and control with Web/App platform.

2. Overview about Architecture and Technology

The robot initially captures its current position, balance system metrics, and images of garbage via the camera, forwarding them to the microprocessor for processing. Following data processing, priority is given to value fusion and noise handling in the robotic system. The resultant priority value is then transmitted through the LoRa module by the microprocessor. Gateways capture the data sent from the LoRa module, directing it to servers dedicated to IoT devices like The Thing Network. Subsequently, data is transmitted via the MQTT protocol to local servers for real-time display and necessary monitoring.

End-users can interact with the system through the installation of an application or website access. The server automatically connects to the nearest device, allowing users to track their robot's journey, location, and other pertinent information. Users have the option to define the robot's permissible movement area by selecting positions on a map to create a polygonal region.

Figure 1: System Architecture

Figure 2: Web Platform and Demo prototype

3. Anticipated Impact

A technological breakthrough in waste collection is revolutionizing the fight against aquatic pollution. By harnessing the power of automation this system applied image processing and pathfinding algorithms to gather floating debris from water surfaces efficiently. This critical innovation safeguards marine ecosystems, thereby reducing seafood contamination risks. Ultimately, by enhancing scenic beauty and preventing odours, this solution fosters a more enjoyable environment for both tourists and residents.

4. Potential Challenges

Piloting an autonomous trash-collecting robot using LoRaWAN technology in water may face gauntlets such as balancing the robot's movement with water currents, avoiding getting stuck in shallows, optimizing trash collection routes and battery lifespan, throwing curveballs at its performance by environmental factors.

5. Collaboration Opportunities

The project offers collaboration opportunities with local environmental agencies and governmental authorities to deploy water surface waste-cleaning robot. This collaboration aims to establish

standardized safety protocols and waste disposal methods, integrate IoT systems into existing water infrastructure, and conduct joint research to continually enhance safety measures and waste management. Partnering with academic institutions can foster innovation, ensuring continuous improvement and the development of best practices in water surface waste cleaning, contributing to the overarching goal of environmental protection.

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